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Clinical Cases

Low-Lying Placenta Treated with Homoeopathy

August 17, 2024 • 1 Comment • by Sunil Namdeorao Pawar, Rizwan Ahmed Shabbir Shaikh

Drs. Sunil Namdeorao Pawar and Rizwan Ahmed Shabbir Shaikh share a case of low-lying placenta in a woman of 34, treated successfully with homoeopathy

Abstract

Placenta praevia is a condition/ problem during pregnancy when the placenta completely or partially covers the cervix.

Symptoms:

- The main symptom of placenta praevia is bright red vaginal bleeding without pain after 20 weeks of pregnancy.
- Sometimes only spotting before an event with more blood loss

- In some cases, bleeding doesn't occur until labor. **Risk factor:**
- More common in women who have had babies or had previous H/o Cesarean section/ had scar on uterus from previous surgery/ had placenta previa with previous pregnancy/ are pregnant after having assisted reproductive technique procedure for treatment of infertility/ having twin pregnancy age 3 years or older/ smoking etc.

Complications:

1. Life threatening vaginal bleeding
2. Preterm birth due to Cesarean section due to bleeding
3. Placenta accrete spectrum (here placenta grows into or through the wall of the uterus)

CASE SUMMARY

This is a 34-year-old lady diagnosed with low lying placenta. The case presented is documented in Ahmednagar Homoeopathic Medical College, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra.

The patient was treated with individualized homoeopathic medicine over seven months. Medicine was given only two times in the span of seven months. There were significant changes in the USG reports and finally the placenta migrated to fundoposterior position (normal position) and in July 2023 she delivered a healthy baby with LSCS as she had h/o previous LSCS

CASE RECORD

Mrs. XYZ, a doctor by profession, came with complaint of low-lying placenta

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Along with this the only complaint was dry cough since conception not responding to any treatment, and it was more violent at night time especially in bed.

P/H: previous LSCS 2 times, first in 2012 and second 2016. LSCS in 2012 was done due to premature rupture of membrane during 9th month of pregnancy and in 2016 LSCS was done as an emergency due to PV bleeding during 8th month due to mild detachment of placenta as it was also low lying covering internal Os fully. Due to these events she was very anxious in this pregnancy after her ultrasound.

Her nature is mild and she is very emotional, extroverted, makes friends easily, avoids quarrels and cares about other's sufferings. She is lean, thin, having fair complexion, 5'5" in height, chilly patient. F/H: no family history of placenta previa, Her mother is diabetic and on allopathic treatment and her father has a cardiac history.

Ultrasound done on 26th Jan 2023 before start of treatment Gestational age: 11 weeks, 1 day

1. Placenta right posterior-lateral wall, Low lying, lower margin covering internal os completely (images provided)

Following symptoms were considered for repertorization

- Complete- Female Genitalia- Uterus- Placenta Previa
- Complete-Cough-Dry- Night
- Complete—cough- Violent
- Complete Cough-Evening-Bed in
-

Repertorization was done using Complete repertory and reportorial results are shown in the table below.

PRESCRIPTION: SEPIA 30 stat given on 31st Jan 2023 + Sac-Lac 4 pills TDS for 15 days

The medicine Sepia was selected on individualization, totality of symptoms and confirmation from Materia Medica

Table of Follow ups

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Date	Symptoms	Remedy Prescribed
15/02/2023	Cough decreased significantly, Doing normal routine work	SL / TDS/ 15 days
03/03/2023	No complaints, Doing normal routine work USG: 2/3/23 Gest. age: 16 weeks 1 day Placenta Posterior wall, Low lying, Lower margin 2.7 cm from Internal Os	SL / TDS / 1 month
10/04/2023	Dry cough Increased, No other complaints, Doing normal routine work USG: 7/4/23 Gest. age: 21 weeks 2 days Placenta Right Postero-Lateral wall, Low lying, Lower margin 2.8 cm from Internal Os	SEPIA 200 Stat given SL / TDS / 1 month
24/05/2023	Patient came 15 days late for follow up as there was no complaints and Patient doing normal routine work	SL / TDS / 1 month

	Gest .age: 27 weeks 6 days	RESEARCH VETERINARY
	Placenta Right Fundo-Posterior, Low lying, Lower margin 5.5 cm from Internal Os	
20/06/2023	No complaints, Doing normal routine work	SL / TDS / 1 month
12/07/2023	No complaints, Working stopped since 10 days USG: 11/7/23 Gest.age: 34 weeks 6 days Placenta Right Fundo-Posterior, Normal, Grade III maturity and NO Previa	SL / TDS / 1 month Adv: Planned LSCS in Last week of July

The lady delivered healthy baby on 21st July 2023 with Planned LSCS

Conclusion:

1. After taking Sepia 30 the dry cough started to decrease and patient was feeling better and subsequently there was improvement in Ultrasound also.
2. In April 2023 Sepia 200 stat was given due to increase in cough and ultrasound changes were consistently showing improvement.
3. The main thing was that as patient was a doctor and was running her clinic for 10-12 years, she was able to run her clinic normally till 9th month which she was not able to do in her second pregnancy

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Dr Kalpana Sharad Thube

August 18, 2024 at 10:04 am

Nice case of low lying Placenta treated with Sepia 👍🙌👍
congratulations 🌸🌸

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